

Fredrik Abbors | Dragos Truscan | Tanwir Ahmad

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Fredrik Abbors
Dragos Truscan
Tanwir Ahmad

Åbo Akademi University, Department of Information Technology
Joukahaisenkatu 3-5 A, 20520 Turku, Finland
{fabbors, dtruscan, tahmad}@abo.fi

Abstract

We present a tool-supported approach on creating load models that can be used for performance testing. The models are created automatically from historical web access log data. The result is a stochastic model represented by Probabilistic Timed Automata (PTA) and describes how users interact with a system. Stochastic models have more advantages over traditional models that simply play back scripted or pre-recorded traces: they are easier to create and maintain and achieve higher coverage of the tested application. The purpose of these models is to mimic real user behavior as closely as possible when generating load.

Keywords: Workload model generation, Log File analysis, Performance testing, Probabilistic timed automata.

TUCS Laboratory
Software Engineering Laboratory

1 Introduction

Cloud-based services and applications are becoming increasingly popular. Today they are practically all around us even if we do not realize it. If a user is not satisfied with a particular web site or web service within a relatively short time period, the user is likely to abandon the web site and choose another one [9]. It has long been known that users do not only care about the functionality of a web site; performance is equally important. Further, the workload on a particular web site can change quite rapidly due to e.g., positive exposure on social media sites such as Facebook or Instagram. Hence, it is important to make sure that a web site meets its performance demands [4]. In addition, from a load testing point of view it is important to understand how previous users have used the system and what were their traversal patterns.

The primary idea in performance testing is to establish how well a system performs in terms of responsiveness, stability, resource utilization, etc, under a given synthetic workload. The synthetic workload is usually generated from some kind of workload profile either on-the-fly or pre-generated. However, Ferrari states that synthetic workload should mimic the expected workload as closely as possible [7], otherwise it is not possible to draw any reliable conclusions from the results. This means that if load is generated from a workload model, then the model must represent the real-world user behavior as closely as possible. In addition, Jain points out that one of the most common mistakes in load testing is the use of unrepresentative load [2].

There already exists a broad range of well established web analytics software both as open source (Analog, AWStats, Webalyzer), proprietary (Sawmill, NetInsight, Urchin), as well as web hosted ones (Google Analytics, Analyzer, Insight). All these tools have different pricing models and range from free up to several hundred euros per month. These tools provide all kinds of information regarding the user clients, different statistics, daily number of visitors, average site hits, etc. Some tools can even visualize paths that visitors take on the site. However, this usually requires a high-priced premium subscription. What the above tools do not provide is a deeper classification of the users or even an artefact that can directly be used for load testing. Such an artefact, based on real user data, would be the ideal source for generating synthetic load in a performance testing environment. Instead, the performance tester has to interpret the provided information and build his own artefact, from where load is generated. Automatically creating this artefact would also significantly speed up the performance testing process by removing the need of manual labour, and thus saving time and money.

This paper investigates an approach for automatically creating a workload model from web server log data. More specifically, we are targeting HTTP-based systems with *RESTful* [14] interfaces. The proposed approach uses the K-means algorithm to classify users into groups based on the requested resources and a probabilistic workload model is automatically built for each group.

The presented approach and its tool support integrates with our performance testing process using the *MBPeT* [1] tool. The *MBPeT* tool generates load in real-time by executing the workload models in parallel. The parallel execution is meant to simulate the concurrent nature of normal web requests coming from real world users. The tool itself has a distributed master/slave architecture which means that it is suitable for the cloud. However, the approach can be used independently for analyzing and classifying the usage of a web site.

The rest of the paper is structured as follow: In Section 2, we present the formalism behind the workload models that we use. In Section 3, we cover the methodology whereas, in Section 4, we present the tool support. Section 5 shows our approach applied on a real world example. In Section 6, we demonstrate the validity of our work. Finally, in Section 7, we present our conclusions and discuss future work.

2 The Process

In our performance testing process we make use of the model-based performance testing tool *MBPeT* [1]. In our process, the prerequisite is the workload model. Since the workload model is the central element, from where load is generated, it is important that it describes the behavior of the user as closely as possible, otherwise it is not possible to draw any reliable conclusions from the results. Creating a model without information regarding user behavior might be difficult. However, log data describes exactly how the users are behaving but it is not structured in a way understood by humans. If log data is available, it should be possible to generate a model that represent the user behavior. Figure 1 depicts the process we are using. This technical report will concentrate on the left part of the figure, i.e. how we transition from log data and end up with a workload model.

Figure 1: Performance testing process

2.1 Workload models

Traditionally, performance testing starts first with identifying key performance scenarios, based on the idea that certain scenarios are more frequent than others or certain scenarios impact more on the performance of the system than other scenarios. A performance scenario is a sequence of actions performed by an identified group of users [12]. However, this has traditionally been a manual step in the performance testing process. Typically, the identified scenarios are put together in a model or subprogram and later executed to produce load that is sent to the system.

In our approach, we use *probabilistic timed automaton* (PTA) [8] to model the likelihood of user actions. The PTAs consists of a set of *locations* interconnected to each other via a set of *edges*. A PTA also includes the notion of time and probabilities (see Figure 2(a)). Edges are labeled with different values: *probability value*, *think time*, and *action*. The *probability value* represents the likelihood of that particular edge being taken based on a probability mass function. The *think time* describes the amount of time that a user thinks or waits between two consecutive actions. An *action* is a request or a set of requests that the user sends to the system. Executing an action means making a probabilistic choice, waiting for the specified think time, and executing the actual action. In order to reduce complexity of the PTA, we use a compact notation where the probability value, think time, and action are modeled on the same edge (see Figure 2(b)).

3 The Methodology

In this section, we will describe the methodology of our approach and discuss relevant aspects in more detail. The starting point of our approach is a web server log provided by web servers such as Apache and Microsoft Server. The log is processed in several steps and a workload model is produced. We start with a log file or a set of log files that are analyzed and from which a workload model is created.

3.1 Data Cleaning

Before we parse the log file we prepare and clean up the data. This entails that irrelevant data is removed from the log. This could be e.g., lines that start with a pound sign (“#”) or some other unwanted characters. This usually indicate that the line is to be interpreted as a comment and not as a log entry.

Nowadays, it is not uncommon to encounter requests made by autonomous machines, also referred to as bots, usually used to crawl the web and index web site. These types of requests are identified and removed from the log into a separate list. The commonly known bots are specified in a whitelist that can be updated by the user. Requests from bots are detected in two ways. Firstly, by looking at the

(a) Original PTA

(b) Compact PTA

Figure 2: Example of a probabilistic timed automata

resource that has been requested. Some bots usually request a specific resource, namely *robots.txt*. This file contains information of what the bots should not index on the site. Secondly, we can refer bots from the user agent that made the request. It is not uncommon that the name of the user agent contains the word bot e.g., *Googlebot* or *Bingbot*. At the moment we are only interested in HTTP requests that result in a success or redirect i.e., requests that start with 2xx or 3xx. Since requests that result in an error, typically requests that starts with 4xx or 5xx, are not usually part of the intended behavior they are put in a separate list.

3.2 Parsing

The cleaned log file is parsed line by line using a pattern that matches the logging format. In our approach, a new virtual user is created when a new client IP-address¹ is encountered in the log. For each request made to the sever, the requested resource is stored in a list associated with a virtual user. The date and

¹Our approach uses IP-addresses for user classification since the UserId is only available for authenticated users and usually not present in the log.

time information of the request together with the time difference to the previous request is also stored. The latter is what we denote as *think time* between two requests. For example, consider the requests in Table 1. The information would result in two new virtual users (Alice and Bob) being created. Bob made a request for a document while Alice made requests for two different pictures. The time between Alice’s two requests was 34 seconds. This is what we note as *think time* between two requests. Please note, that it is impossible to know what the think time was before the first request, since we have no information about what Alice before then. This will be important later on when we divide requests into different sessions.

Client IP-address	User-Identifier	User Id	Date	Requested Resource	HTTP Status Code	Size of Object
136.242.54.78	example.site.com	alice	[20/Aug/2013:23:22:27 -0700]	"GET /pics/sunset_pg.gif HTTP/1.0"	200	2326
87.153.57.43	example.site.com	bob	[20/Aug/2013:23:22:35 -0500]	"GET /documents/doc1.pdf HTTP/1.0"	200	15895
136.242.54.78	example.site.com	alice	[20/Aug/2013:23:23:01 -0700]	"GET /pics/building12.png HTTP/1.0"	200	1583

Table 1: Example of a Apache web server logging format

3.3 Pre-processing

From the previous step, we obtain a list of virtual users and for each virtual user a list of requests made from the same client IP-address. In the pre-processing phase, these lists of requests are split up into shorter list called *sessions*. A session is a sequence of requests made to the web server that represent the activity that a user does in a certain time interval. It is not always trivial to say when one sessions ends and another begins, since the time interval varies from session to session. Traditionally, a session ends when a certain period of inactivity is detected, e.g., 30 minutes. Hence, we define a session *timeout value* which is used to split the list of requests of a given user into sessions. In other words, we are searching for a time gap between two successive requests from the same virtual user that is greater than the specified timeout value. When a gap is found, the request trace is split into a new session. Figure 3 shows in more detail how a list of requests gets broken down into shorter sessions. In the example, a timeout value of 30 minutes is used.

3.4 Building a Request Tree

Visitors interact with web sites by carrying out *actions*. Actions can be seen as abstract transactions or templates that fit many different requests. In this step, we go in reverse by trying to deduce which requests are the result of what action. For example, consider a normal web shop where users add products to a basket. Adding two different products to the basket will result in two different web requests even though the action is the same.

To achieved this, we first order the requests into a tree structure. Consider the example in table 2. This example illustrates a short log file as the result of requests

Figure 3: Example showing how a list of requests are split into shorter sessions

being made to a web server. We split the request string by the "/" separator and structure it into a tree. Figure 4-left shows how the requests in Table 2 would be structured. We always keep count of how many times we end up in a leaf node.

After parsing a log file, we obtain a large tree that might be difficult to manage. However, the tree can be reduced into a smaller tree by grouping nodes together. Consider the second request made by both Bob and Alice in table 2. These two requests are basically the same type of request. They both request a resource from the same collection. This is similar to a *REST* interface where one uses collections and resources. It would seem obvious that these two requests are the result of the same type of action, only that the user requested different resources. Hence, by grouping together requests of the same type, the tree can be reduced to a smaller tree. Requests that are grouped together in this way is called an *action*. Figure 4-right shows how a tree can be reduced into a smaller tree. The algorithm is recursive and nodes in the tree are grouped together if they share joint sub-nodes. Requests in the tree can also be joined by manually inspecting the tree

and grouping nodes that are a result of the same action. Once the request tree has been reduced as much as possible, every path in the reduced tree, that reach an leaf node, is considered an *action* that can be executed against the system. If a node in the path has more than one parameter, e.g., it is a result of grouping two resources, that part of the request can be parameterized. For example, the request `"/basket/book_42,phone_6/add"` is a parameterized action where either *book_42* or *phone_6* should be used when sending the actual request to the system.

Client IP-address	User-Identifier	User Id	Date	Requested Resource	HTTP Status Code	Size of Object
87.153.57.43	example.site.com	bob	[20/Aug/2013:14:22:35 -0500]	"GET /browse HTTP/1.0"	200	855
87.153.57.43	example.site.com	bob	[20/Aug/2013:14:23:42 -0500]	"GET /basket/book_42/add HTTP/1.0"	200	685
87.153.57.43	example.site.com	bob	[20/Aug/2013:14:23:58 -0500]	"GET /basket/book_42/delete HTTP/1.0"	200	936
136.242.54.78	example.site.com	alice	[21/Aug/2013:23:44:45 -0700]	"GET /browse HTTP/1.0"	200	855
136.242.54.78	example.site.com	alice	[21/Aug/2013:23:46:27 -0700]	"GET /basket/phone_6/add HTTP/1.0"	200	685
136.242.54.78	example.site.com	alice	[21/Aug/2013:23:57:02 -0700]	"GET /basket/view.html HTTP/1.0"	200	1772

Table 2: Requests to be structured in a tree

Figure 4: Example of request tree reduction.

3.5 User Classification

Before we start constructing a workload model representing user behavior, we cluster different virtual users into groups according to their behavior. By user behavior we mean a behavioral pattern that a group of web site visitors have in common. A *User Type* can be seen as a group abstracting several visitors of a

web site. The reason for this is that sometimes a web site or web service can have a group of visitors that behave differently from another group of visitors and a separate workload model for that particular group is desired.

To group visitors based on the actions they perform we use the K-means algorithm [10]. Figure 5 depicts a typical example of clustering data into two groups using K-means. K-means clustering is a old method that involves assigning data points to k different clusters so that it minimizes the total squared distance between each point and its closest cluster center. One of the most widely used algorithms is simply referred to as "K-means" and it is a well documented algorithm that have several proposed optimization. It typically execute as follows:

1. Choose k clusters and initialize the centroid by uniformly choosing a random value from the data points.
2. For every sample in the data set, assign it to the closest cluster using the Euclidean distance.
3. Calculate a new centroid for every cluster by computing the average of all sample in the cluster.
4. Repeat step 2 and 3 until the clusters no longer changes.

Figure 5: Example of two dimensional K-means clustering

Table 3 shows the properties used for clustering. The properties are the *actions* obtained from the reduced request tree and the numbers represent the number of times a visitor has performed that action. Figure 6 show how the different visitors in Table 3 would be clustered into groups (or *User Types*) using the K-means algorithm. The only input in this step is the number of desired clusters which has to be specified a priori.

Our approach also allows us to cluster virtual users based on other characteristics. Table 4 shows an example using different clustering parameters. Here

Virtual User	Action1	Action2	Action3	Action4	Action5
Visitor 1	2	0	0	3	3
Visitor 2	0	3	4	3	3
Visitor 3	1	0	1	8	9
Visitor 4	4	6	0	0	1
Visitor 5	0	0	4	8	7
Visitor 6	5	2	0	7	0

Table 3: Example showing the number of actions that different visitors perform.

Figure 6: K-means clustering on data from Table 3

the variable *#Get* means the total number of GET requests sent to the system and *#Post* means the total number of POST requests sent to the system. *ATT* stands for Average Think Time, *ASL* stands for Average Session Length, and *ADT* stands for Average Response Size

Virtual User	#Get	#Post	ATT	ASL	ARS
Visitor 1	25	3	44	653	696
Visitor 2	17	0	25	277	1353
Visitor 3	31	3	54	1904	473
Visitor 4	19	1	23	444	943

Table 4: Example showing different clustering parameters.

This method, however, gives a different clustering result than the method presented previously and can be used as a complement if the first method gives an unsatisfied result.

3.6 Removing Infrequent Sessions

Before we start building the workload model for each selected cluster, we filter out low frequency sessions. If we would include all possible sessions in the final workload model it would become too cluttered and difficult to understand and would include actions which do not contribute significantly to the load due to their low frequency rate. We are mainly interested in the common group behavior among visitors in the same cluster.

Removing sessions that have low frequency is achieved by sorting the sessions in descending order according to their execution rate. We filter out low frequent sessions according to a Pareto probability density function [3] by cutting off the tail beneath a certain threshold value. The threshold value is given as a percentage value. That means that sessions below the threshold are simply ignored and treated as irrelevant. The threshold value can however be adjusted on-the-fly to include more or less sessions in the workload model. Table 5 shows an example of sessions listed in a descending order according to their execution count. There is a total of 20 sessions, some of them have been executed several times, e.g., session 1 has been executed 7 times. A threshold value of 0.7 would in this case mean that we want 70 percent of the most execute sessions included in our model, meaning a total of 14 sessions. Thus, we would have to construct a model with (Session1 * 7) + (Session2 * 6) + (Session3 * 1).

Session	Number of times executed
Session 1	7
Session 2	6
Session 3	3
Session 4	2
Session 5	1
Session 6	1
Total	20

Table 5: Sessions listed in a descending order according to number of times executed

3.7 Building the Workload Model

The workload models that we create describes the common behavior of all virtual users belonging to the same cluster. We say that the model describes the behavior of a particular *User Type*. Creating the model for a particular user type is a step-wise process where we overlap sessions of all visitors belonging to the same cluster.

Session by session we gradually build a model, while reusing existing nodes in the model as much as possible. At each step, we note the number of times an edge

has been traversed, the action, and the think time value. We use this information to calculate the probability and average think time of each edge in the model.

Figure 7 depicts how the workload model is gradually built. One session at a time is included in the workload model. An edge represents an action being sent to the system. The numbers associated to the edges represent session IDs. Each node represents a place, where the visitor waits before sending the next action. One by one we include all the sessions belonging to the same cluster, while reusing existing nodes as much as possible. Identical sessions will be laid on top of each other and at each step, we note the number of times an edge has been traversed, the action, and the think time value. We use this information to calculate the probability and average think time of each edge.

Figure 7: Model built in a step-wise manner.

We calculate the probability for an action going out from a state according to:

$$\mathbf{P}_{a_i}^s = \frac{\mathbf{N}_{a_i}^s}{\mathbf{N}_a^s} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_{a_i}^s$ denotes the probability P of a particular action a_i going out from state s . $\mathbf{N}_{a_i}^s$ denotes the total number of times an action a_i has left state s and \mathbf{N}_a^s means the total number of times all actions a has left state s .

In a similar way we calculate the average think time of an action going out from a state according to:

$$\overline{\mathbf{TT}}_{a_i}^s = \frac{\sum_{j=0}^n \mathbf{TT}_{a_{ij}}^s}{\mathbf{N}_{a_i}^s} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{TT}_{a_i}^s$ denotes the think time TT of an action a_i leaving state s . $\mathbf{TT}_{a_{ij}}$ describes one time think value of an action leaving state s . $\mathbf{N}_{a_i}^s$ means the total

number of a action a_i leaving state s .

Figure 8: Root model describing different user types their waiting times and probability

Figure 9: Waiting time between sessions of a user

In order to guarantee that the workload generated from the model matches the workload present in the log file, we calculate the user arrival rate. This information together with the distribution between user types is described in a higher level model called the *root model*. Figure 8 depicts such a model. The values are separated by a "/" and refer to the probability, waiting time, and user type, respectively. The probability value describes the distribution between different user types. The waiting time describes how long the users are waiting between sessions. The user type value simply denotes what workload model to execute. To calculate the waiting time of a user type, we first have to study the waiting time between different sessions of a particular user. Figure 9 describes the phenomena in more detail. We calculate the time between two sessions according to:

$$\mathbf{TBS}_i^k = S_{st_{i+1}}^k - S_{end_i}^k \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{TBS}_i^k denotes the time between session i and $i+1$ belonging to cluster k . $S_{st_{i+1}}^k$ means the start time of session $i+1$ and $S_{end_i}^k$ means the end time of session i .

The average time between sessions for a particular user is calculated according to:

$$\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}_i^k = \frac{\sum_{j=0}^{N_s^i-1} \mathbf{TBS}_j^i}{N_s^i} \quad (4)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}_i^k$ denotes the average time between sessions ($\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}$) for user i belonging to cluster k . \mathbf{TBS}_j^i means the time between sessions (\mathbf{TBS}) of session j belonging to user i . N_s^i means the total number of sessions s belonging to user i .

The average time between sessions for an entire cluster (or user type) is calculated according to:

$$\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}^k = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N_k} \overline{\mathbf{TBS}}_i^k}{N_k} \quad (5)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}^k$ means the time between sessions for a cluster or user type k . $\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}_i^k$ denotes the average time between sessions ($\overline{\mathbf{TBS}}$) for user i belonging to cluster k . N_k means the total number of users in a cluster k

The probability value of a user type or cluster is calculated according to

$$\mathbf{P}^k = \frac{N_i^k}{N_i} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{P}^k denotes the probability P for a user type or cluster k . N_i^k means the total number of users i in cluster k . N_i means the total number of users.

4 Tool support

In this section we will describe the tool support for our approach. The tool was implemented using the Python [13] programming language. To increase the performance of the tool and make use of as many cores as possible to the most time consuming tasks, we made use of Python's multiprocessing library. Our tool has a set of pre-defined patterns for common logging formats that are typically used in modern web servers, i.e. Apache, Microsoft Server, etc. However, if the pattern of the log file is not automatically recognized (e.g., due to a custom logging format) the user can manually specify a logging pattern in terms of a regular expression. Once the log is parsed, the data is stored into a database. This way we avoid having to re-parse large log files from one experiment to another.

Before parsing a log file, the tool prompts the user for a session time out value and the number of groups to cluster users in. Once the file has been parsed and the reduced request tree has been built, the user has a chance to manually inspect the tree and manipulate. Requests can be grouped manually by dragging one node on top of the other. Figure 10 shows an example of the request tree. However, if desired, this step can be fully automated.

Figure 10: Example of the request tree

When the workload models have been built for each cluster they are presented to the user. Figure 11 shows an example where 2 clusters have been used. On the left side of the figure, the tool shows the number of concurrent users throughout the logging period. The slider bar at the bottom of the figure can be used to adjust the threshold values, which determines how many sessions to include in the workload model. A higher value means more sessions will be considered when constructing the workload model. A higher threshold value usually means more sessions are included in the model, leading to a more complex model.

Besides just creating the workload models, the tool also creates an adapter code. The adapter code is used to connect abstract actions found in the model to callable methods which will send parameterized requests to the system under test. Naturally, the adapter code also integrates with our performance testing tool *MBPeT*.

Figure 11: The output window

5 Example

In this section, we apply our approach to a web log file containing real users data. We realize that it is difficult to obtain log files from systems where real users are interacting. One of the reasons is of course due to confidentiality. Most companies do not want to reveal log file information because the files themselves might contain sensitive information about their customers. Also, log files taken from various web caches are not sufficient since they contain requests to numerous different web sites and services. Even if only one particular web site or service were filtered out, it is usually not enough of data to infer a model. The web site² used in this example maintains scores of football games played in the football league called *pubiliiga*. The web site also stores information about where and when the games are played, rules, teams, etc. The web site has been created using the Django framework [6] and runs on top of an Apache web server.

²www.pubiliiga.fi

5.1 Data Cleaning

The log that we used, was 323MB in size and contained roughly 1.3 million lines of log data. The web site was visited by 20,000 unique users that resulted in 365,000 page views between April 25th of 2009 and August 23rd of 2013. However, most of the users only visited the web site once or twice and there was only about 2000 frequent users that regularly visited the web site. Also, since the web site is updated frequently on the same platform on which it is was running, the log contained a lot of data that from erroneous requests made by the simple method of trail and error during development. All the erroneous requests and requests made from known robots were filtered out. The results that we are going to show in this section are generated from a mere 30,000 lines of log data generated by 1143 unique users.

5.2 Processing

We used a session timeout value of 60 minutes to determine how to split the list of requests into shorter sessions. In this experiment, we clustered the users into two different groups. The total time to parse and pre-process the data took around 10 seconds. The computer was equipped with a 8 core Intel i7 2.93 GHz processor and had 16 GB of memory.

Table 6 shows a summary of the execution time for different steps of the algorithm for different log sizes. The final step, constructing the workload model, was purposely left out since it varies considerably depending on the chosen number of clusters and threshold value.

Phase	30.000	50.000	100.000	200.000	400.000
Parsing	6 sec	10 sec	22 sec	50 sec	2 min
Pre-processing	4 sec	9 sec	10 sec	21 sec	31 sec
Request tree reduction	0.3 sec	0.3 sec	0.8 sec	2 sec	5 sec
Clustering	0.08 sec	0.08 sec	0.4 sec	5 sec	60 sec
Total	10.38 sec	19.38 sec	33.2 sec	1 min 18 sec	3 min 36 sec

Table 6: Table showing execution times for different log sizes in terms of lines of log entries.

5.3 Results

Figure 12 shows the constructed workload models for one of the clusters. A total of 985 virtual users were grouped into this cluster. Figure 12(a) shows the workload model when using a threshold value of 0.5, which means that 50 percent of the traces are included in the model, starting from the high frequent ones. However, the model is too complicated to be used for analysis, and some of the sessions are rarely executes. Figure 12(b) shows the workload model with a threshold

(a) Workload model for cluster 1, (threshold = 50%).

(b) Workload model for cluster 1, (threshold = 30%).

Figure 12: Models recreated from log data.

value of 0.3, meaning that 30 percent of the traces are included in the model starting from the high frequent ones. Here we can see that the model is much more readable and we can actually start to make sense of the navigational patterns in the workload model. For confidentiality reasons the actual request types have been left of and replaced by abstract types. The workload models created for the second cluster looked almost the same. Creating the models took approximately 2 seconds. However, the execution time may hugely vary depending on the number of sessions that need to be included in the workload model. That number of sessions included in the model depends on what threshold value is used.

6 Validation

In this section, we demonstrate the validity of our approach by using it on a auctioning web service, generically called YAAS (Yet Another Auction Site). The

YAAS web service was developed as a university stand-alone project. The web service has a *RESTful* interface and has 5 simple actions that a user can perform:

- Browse: Returns all active auctions.
- Search: Returns auctions that matches the search query.
- Get_Auction: Returns information about a particular auction.
- Get_Bids: Returns all the bids made to a particular auction.
- Bid: Allows an authenticated user to place a bid on an auction.

In this experiment we ran two load tests. In load test 1 we generated load from a workload model that we built manually. In load test 2 we generated load from a workload generated from the resulted log file of load test 1. To validate the approach we decided to compare the the two workload models. We also compared the load that was generated in the two tests. We will later present the results. In the first load test, we manually created models for two different user types. To test if the clustering really works as expected, we made the workload models almost identical except for one request. One user type is doing distinctively a search request while the other user type is always doing a browse request. If the algorithm can cluster user into different groups when only one action distinguishes them, then we consider it to be good enough. Figure 13 shows the models that were manually designed.

6.1 Generating a log file

Once the models were built, they were used to load test the YAAS system using our in-house performance testing tool *MBPeT*. We simulated 10 virtual users in parallel for 2 hours, all using different IP-addresses, in order to produce a log file. The resulting log file contained roughly 10,000 lines of data (9903 lines to be exact). We set the virtual users to wait 20 seconds between each session. This value is later going to guide us in where to split the sessions. From the log data that was generated during load testing of the YAAS system, we then tried to recreate the original models as accurately as possible. Please note that the original model is of a probabilistic nature, which means that distinctly different traces with different lengths can be generated from fairly simple model. For example, in this experiment, the shortest session had only 1 action, while the longest session had 22 actions. Also, we don't have exact control over how many time each trace is executed by a user.

(a) User Type 1 original model.

(b) User Type 2 original model.

Figure 13: Original workload models from which load was generated.

(a) User Type 1 recreated model.

(b) User Type 2 recreated model

Figure 14: Workload model recreated from the original log data.

6.2 Recreating the models

To make sure that we split the sessions at the right spot we used a timeout value of 20 seconds. No other delay between any request was that large. Since we are going to recreate the workload models from log data, we clustered the user into 2 types. Each user type is later going to be represented with a separate workload model. In this experiment we did not filter out any user sessions, hence we used a threshold value of 1.0, meaning all traces found in the log were used to recreate the models. Figure 14 shows the output models that was generated. As one can see, the only difference from the original models is the probability values on the edges. However close, the probability values on the edges in the original models does not match exactly those in the generated workload models (compare Figure 13 to Figure 14). This is due to the fact that we use stochastic model and we don't have exact control of what traces that are generated. Figure 15 shows the original and the generated root models.

Figure 15: Root models

6.3 Data Gathering

Even though the models look similar, we also wanted to make sure that the load generated from the original models matched the load generated from our recreated models. Hence, we let the MBPeT tool measure the number of requests sent to the YAAS system during both load tests. Table 7 shows a comparison between the test runs.

Request	Load Test 1	Load Test 2
Search(string)	1263	1294
Browse()	1895	1942
Get_Auction(id)	2762	2821
Get_bids(id)	2697	2625
Bid(id, price, username, password)	1288	1265
Total	9903	9947
Request Rate	1,37 req/sec	1,38 req/sec

Table 7: Comparison between the two test runs

As can be seen from the table, using the recreated model during load test 2, resulted in slightly higher work load. However, we like to point out the the load test lasted for 2 hours and we see a difference of 44 requests. This is backed up by looking at the measured request rate. Load test 1 had 1,37 requests per second while load test 2 is virtually identical with 1,37 request per se. MBPeT also shows how the requests are spread over time. Figure 16 shows the workload as a function of request (actions) over time for both tests.

From the figure one can see that the graphs are not identical but but the trend and scale is pretty much similar.

7 Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented a tool-supported approach for creating performance models from historical log data. The models are of a stochastic nature

(a) Load Test 1

(b) Load Test 2

Figure 16: Number of request shows as a function over time

and specify the probabilistic distribution of actions that are executed against the system.

The approach is automated, hence reducing the effort necessary to create workload models for performance testing. In contrast, Cai et al. [5] report that they spent around 18 hours to manually create a test plan and the JMeter scripts

for the reference Java PetStore application [11].

The experiments presented in this paper have shown that the approach can adequately enough create workload models from log files and they mimic the real user behavior when used for load testing. Further, the models themselves give insight in how users behave. This information can be valuable for optimizing functions in the system and enforcing certain navigational patterns on the web site.

Future work will targeted towards handling larger amount of log data. Currently the tool is not optimized enough to operate efficiently on large data amounts. Another improvement is automatic session detection. Currently the tool follows a pre-defined timeout value for detecting sessions. Automatic session detection could suggest different timeout values for different users, hence, improving on the overall quality of the recreated model. Currently, we are only clustering users according to accessed resources. In the future, we would like to extend the K-means clustering algorithm to cluster based on other relevant factors like: request method, size of resource, user request rate, etc. This clustering method could suggest models that, when executed, exercise the workload patterns on the system, thus, potentially finding "hidden" bottlenecks. Further, an interesting experiment would be to analyze only failed or dropped requests. This way one could for instance study the details of how a DoS-attack was carried out and what pages were hit during the attack.

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The logo features a dark blue background with several thin, white, abstract lines that create a sense of movement and connectivity, resembling a network or a stylized map. The text is positioned on the left side of this blue area.

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